

Development of Cognitive Independence of Students - as the Content of Professional and Pedagogical Activity of Future Teachers

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Abstract: The importance and development of cognitive independence in education is analyzed in this article. Cognitive independence refers to the development of students' independent thinking, problem-solving and learning abilities. The article examines how this concept is implemented through pedagogical approaches, what role it plays in the educational process, and the importance of modern methods. Also, the importance of improving the quality of methodological approaches and educational materials necessary for the development of cognitive independence is emphasized.

Keywords: Communicativeness, general secondary education, student, competence, school practice, ability, personality development, reflection.

Cognitive independence means a student's ability to think independently, solve problems, understand information, and gain knowledge. Ensuring students' cognitive independence is widely researched as a pedagogical approach. Tasks used in the educational process should be organized based on this approach. Tasks formed on the basis of this approach form and develop students' important skills such as independent thinking, sorting information from a large amount of information and sources, being able to use different learning strategies in acquiring knowledge, and finding the optimal solution to a problem. Cognitive independence describes the ability of a student as a cognitively independent individual to consciously control his mental processes, analyze information, draw conclusions, and act independently without constant guidance from others.

The problem of developing students' cognitive independence is one of the urgent issues of pedagogy and psychology that is increasing year by year. Pupils' interaction with the environment, communication, its activity and activity are carried out through cognitive processes. Cognitive independence is an integral part of students' cognitive abilities, mental qualities, initiative and individuality.

Cognitive independence is a socially significant quality of a person and is formed in various types of activities of students. The problem of developing cognitive independence is considered in various works of teachers and psychologists. Ya. A. Komensky, K. D.

Ushinsky, D. Lok, Jean-Jacques Rousseau defined cognitive activity as the natural desire of preschoolers to learn. M.A. Kholodnaya , T.M. Golovastikova , S.M. Vishnyakova , L.L. Timofeeva , G.I. Sukina and others studied the characteristics of cognitive activity and how to activate it in preschoolers.

In research on "cognitive independence" there are descriptions of it as a "pedagogical phenomenon" or "a two-way interdependent process". "Cognitive independence" can be considered subjectively and objectively.

In the explanatory dictionary of terms formed under the leadership of teacher scientist O. Musurmonova, the term "cognitive" is defined as "independent thinking process of a person".

In her scientific article, G. Sultonova, filling in the content given in the above definition, elaborates that "cognitiveness" is the process of processing and perception of a person, including some highly developed primates, receiving information and information that comes in different ways.

The term "cognitive independence" (English "cognitive independence") represents a unique learning environment and is considered as a pedagogical approach in pedagogical practice. The emergence and development of this approach is mainly based on cognitive psychology and educational theories. In the 1950s and 1960s, the founders of cognitive psychology, Jean Piaget and Jerome Bruner, were introduced to science. This approach represents an exploration of ideas about how independently a person can form his knowledge.

A.K. Markova shows that the manifestation of cognitive independence depends on cognitive motives. Cognitive motives are divided into three types: broad cognitive motives (new knowledge, evidence, events and situations); educational cognitive motives (methods of acquiring knowledge, orientation to mastering); self-development motives (directed to additional knowledge, independent self-improvement).

M.D. Vinogradov and I.B. Pervin emphasized that collective cognitive activity plays an important role in the development of cognitive independence in students. Through this, students' creativity, creativity, imagination and independence are encouraged. By teaching students to work in a team, the ability to communicate, to listen to others' opinions with patience and respect, and to express constructive opinions is developed. Mutual respect, attentiveness, formation of a positive attitude to learning new knowledge and respect for individual interest in educational groups are important components of collective cognitive activity.

In some pedagogical studies, it is noted that not all teaching methods develop cognitive independence. Cognitive activity is carried out by students only when they motivate themselves to be active. Cognitive activity is determined by the attitude to the studied knowledge, that is, the subjective position. Students are not only the object of learning, but also the subject of learning. Pupils not only fulfill the requirements of the teacher, but also carry out internal adjustment according to their personal experience, level of mental development, actively absorb and process new knowledge.

Cognitive independence is a complex psychological and pedagogical concept. According to S.M. Vishnyakov, cognitive independence is the quality of the learner's educational activities, his attitude to the content and process of education, his desire to effectively acquire knowledge and skills, his mobilization of moral and voluntary efforts to achieve goals, and is the ability to have aesthetic pleasure.

L.L. Timofeva noted that all the information in the educational materials may not be interesting for students, but with the help of a professional approach, students can develop their cognitive independence and organize the educational process in an interesting and effective way. In order to arouse students' desire to learn, it is necessary to develop their need for cognitive independence. In this way, students learn to find interesting aspects in the process itself.

The development of cognitive independence in students is manifested not only in educational activities, but also in independent activities based on subjective experience. This is manifested not only in mastering the content specified in the educational and regulatory documents, but also in objective and social values, in the application of the learned knowledge in practical activities and in the expression of attitudes, as well as in educational communication. Unsuccessful communication between the teacher and students turns into a teacher's monologue. This leads to boredom and alienation of students from the learning process. Therefore, it can be said that the development of cognitive independence of students is based on constant communication.

Cognitive independence encompasses a variety of cognitive abilities, including:

1. Learning to work systematically. The ability to systematically study information, set goals, analyze, evaluate, plan, implement, and select strategies to achieve goals becomes a regular activity in solving any task or problem.
2. Critical thinking. Describes the student's ability to critically analyze information, consider different points of view, and make informed decisions. Critical thinking is important in being able to verify information.
3. Problem solving. Ability to know different approaches and aspects of solving a given problem, evaluate them, use effective methods, and effectively solve complex problems by evaluating and applying solutions.
4. Being able to form opinions independently. Reflections are formed by the ability of students to think independently, reflect on their own learning process, recognize their strengths and weaknesses, and constantly improve them.
5. The ability to learn independently. Cognitive independence develops the ability of all students to find solutions to a task, research, use resources, and use learning strategies individually, not with the same approach.

The development of cognitive independence of students in the preparation of future teachers for professional-pedagogical activity is the main component of their activity. Development of cognitive independence in education is an important pedagogical approach. Teachers should not only convey evidence-based knowledge to students, but also develop independent thinking and learning skills. This helps students prepare not only for specific assignments or exams, but also for independent learning and professional success.

According to Sh. Sharipov, "one of the important factors of individual development of the student is his age-related characteristics" and "each age stage has a direct effect on the character, temperament, abilities and cognitive processes of a person in a way specific to its development factors, laws and changes". In the formation of students' creative abilities, "the main attention should be paid to increasing the weight of the required characteristics, looking at the indicators of activity in all areas as a general set."

In the developed countries of the world in the 21st century, as one of the main directions of modernization of the content of education, the main attention was paid to the issue of introducing the competence approach in education. Because education based on the competence approach is education aimed at forming the ability of students to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and skills in their personal, professional and social activities. In 1996, the Council of Europe organized a Symposium on "Core Competencies for Europe" in which the initial core competencies for the continuing education system of the EU member states were defined.

The ability to search for and find the necessary information, to be able to use it effectively, the competence to work with information through abilities, self-physical, spiritual, mental, intellectual and creative development, striving for perfection, independent study throughout life, cognitive skills and acquires the competence of self-development of life experience,

alternative assessment of one's own behavior and independent decision, can search for the necessary information in the text, and also develops the competence of working with information, which is one of its basic competencies. In addition: a sense of commitment to the processes taking place in society; knowing and observing one's civil duties and rights; social active citizenship competence, loyalty to the motherland, kindness to people, belief in universal and national values through dealing with labor and civil relations and having legal culture; understanding art and works of art; following cultural rules and a healthy lifestyle; national and general cultural competence, ability to make personal, family, professional and economic plans; be able to read various diagrams, drawings and models in daily activities; through the use of science and technology innovations that increase labor productivity, mathematical literacy, awareness and use of science and technology innovations develop.

In an article by researcher Patrick O'Donnell, he summarizes the opinions of several researchers on the question of what qualities secondary school students should have in order to become independent, and suggests that they are: basic skills and knowledge: literacy, numeracy and technology; expanded content: social studies, sciences, languages, arts, coding, and more; critical knowledge: reasoning, problem solving, design thinking, creativity, information analysis; social-emotional: growth mindset, assertiveness, self-awareness, teamwork and cooperation.

Information about knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for independent life is given, and when the role of skills in labor activity is studied according to the demand value, communication competence is in the first place, and team work is in the next place. and trade-service skills. It also examines important knowledge and skills that modern employers want. Along with Industry 4.0, information is given on the evolution of education and vocational training mechanisms.

Without independent education of students, daily-practical competences cannot be fully formed. Guidance and support of students for independent education are also considered as pedagogical conditions for the development of everyday-practical competence. Ensuring students' cognitive independence includes their ability to analyze information, motivational preferences and goal orientation, control their own goals, self-evaluation, cooperative learning strategies in social relations. Motivational preferences are priority factors that encourage and motivate.

Students' skills in "learning to learn" are important in the formation of basic daily-practical competencies through independent education. Students' perfect knowledge of different learning strategies will greatly help them organize their own independent learning process in society. In particular, working with information through various media, social networks, various events, exhibitions, ceremonies, and visits forms the student's competence. A student who has mastered excellent learning strategies can sort the information he needs from the flow of information in society and use it purposefully and productively. Knowing about one's rights and duties as a "consumer" serves the formation of socially active citizenship competence. It helps the student to be able to converse with representatives of different nationalities during different trips, using all recognized standards, and to develop national and general cultural, as well as communicative competences. Of course, in the formation of all daily-practical competences, it is desirable to incorporate the above-mentioned situations into the content of the educational process at school - various situations, situations, norms, values in society, economic and social life as various assignments.

In order to ensure the cognitive independence of students, it is important to use modern methods in classes, to learn by hearing and seeing new information in the process of assimilation. The rapid development of digital competences of students in the conditions of informatization of education does not mean that their other daily-practical competences are also developed at the same time. First of all, thinking, comparison, and analysis are important

in the development of everyday-practical competence. Pedagogical scientist and leading international expert on international evaluation programs A. Shlyakher described the same situation and expressed the following opinion: "Google knows everything. The modern world rewards you based on what you can do with what you know. There is a big difference between them."

Scientific analysis of daily-practical assignments requires, first of all, analysis of the importance of assignments in the educational process. In pedagogical practice, learning strategies based on memorization rarely help students because the tasks they have to perform are becoming more complex and require non-standard analytical skills, which is where digitization starts to solve real problems. In turn, tasks develop by combining new and learned information, creative approach to modern decision-making and finding non-standard solutions. All these will help the students to complete the more complex tasks that are the reflection of tomorrow's world.

Intensification of information processes in society requires the enrichment of educational-methodological complexes aimed at the development of cognitive independence of students with independent learning, repetition, tasks of various complexity that match their abilities, taking into account the psychology of students. Educational materials are not presented in the form of text, but information is given through colorful pictures, graphics, and simple texts. This increases students' motivation towards the lesson material.

In the development of students' cognitive independence, it is important to use modern approaches, tools and methods in lessons, to learn by hearing, seeing and applying new information in the process of assimilation. In recent times, as a result of reforms in the field of education, huge economic growth indicators have been achieved, increasing the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists in all fields. This requires increasing the interest and motivation of students in classes and increasing the attention of teachers to all-round education.

Educational-methodical complexes are of great importance in the development of students' cognitive independence. The purpose of developing educational and methodical sets for general education schools is to "improve the content and quality of educational materials based on the requirements of a competent approach, taking into account the development of modern science and technology, and to effectively apply advanced foreign experience in this field."

In general, the relevance of the problem of developing students' cognitive independence is that their interaction with the outside world takes place only due to their activity and activity, which in turn helps to form independence and initiative. Cognitive independence ensures the student's activity, his passion for knowledge, his movement to determine the known from the unknown. In scientific literature, the concept of "cognitive independence" is expressed in different interpretations. Cognition refers to the student's desire for independent activity, includes social experience, assimilation of methods of activity accumulated by mankind.

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